

Visual Expectations and Haptic Experience in the Perception of Everyday Materials

Campagna, M.^{1,2}, Pastukhov, A.^{1,2,3}, Carbon, C.-C.^{1,2,3}

¹ Department of General Psychology and Methodology, University of Bamberg, Bavaria, Germany

² Research Group EPÆG (Ergonomics, Psychological Aesthetics, Gestalt), Bamberg, Bavaria, Germany

³ Bamberg Graduate School of Affective and Cognitive Sciences (BaGrACS), Bamberg, Bavaria, Germany

Abstract

Material perception in everyday interaction depends on the close interplay of vision and touch. While previous research has clarified important aspects of haptic exploration, less is known about how material qualities are perceived and evaluated in visuo-tactile contexts that also involve cognitive, affective and aesthetic responses. In a first study, we employed 30 right-handed participants who explored 13 everyday material textures in a within-subject design. We used a multi-method paradigm combining self-report measures, think-aloud protocols, eye tracking, pupillometry, and video recording. Participants completed a Touch Perception Task (TPT) while visually and manually exploring the materials. Preliminary findings indicate that materials show distinct explorative profiles and that visual expectations do not always align with haptic experience. Some textures appear more aversive visually than haptically, whereas others become unpleasant only upon touch. The data also suggest substantial individual variation in visuo-tactile evaluation. Together, these findings support a more ecologically grounded approach to material perception, in which sensory, affective, and exploratory dimensions are considered jointly.

Keywords: *Perception, Empirical Aesthetics, Haptic aesthetics, Visuo-tactile perception, Textures perception, Exploration, Think Aloud, Eyetracker*

1 Introduction

Material perception is inherently multisensory. In everyday settings, textures are rarely encountered solely through touch; visual appearance, anticipated feel, and direct haptic input jointly shape how materials are explored and evaluated. Earlier work has shown that specific exploratory procedures support the extraction of haptic properties such as texture, hardness, and temperature^{1,2}. At the same time, empirical aesthetics has shown that material appreciation depends not only on immediate sensory

qualities, but also on complexity, perceptual fluency, and the rewarding effect of discovery^{3,4}. Prior exposure and individual differences, such as Need for Touch, may further modulate these responses^{5,6}. The present work addresses the space between these traditions. While the sensory discrimination of texture is relatively well studied, less is known about how visual anticipation, direct touch, and affective-aesthetic evaluation interact when people engage with real materials under more ecologically grounded conditions. To address this, we developed a multimethod visuo-tactile paradigm combining subjective, qualitative, physiological, and behavioral measures. The aim of first study is to better understand how material properties, visual expectations, and individual differences jointly shape visuo-tactile experience.

2 Methods

Thirty right-handed participants with normal or corrected vision took part in a within-subject laboratory study. Stimuli consisted of 13 everyday material textures varying in micro-geometric and affective properties, including several grades of sandpaper, silks, faux fur, plexiglass, wood, copper, and insulating material. The textures were mounted on rigid cardboard bases to enable comfortable manual exploration.

The experiment comprised three phases. In the preliminary phase, participants provided consent, demographic information, completed a visual acuity check, and filled out individual-difference measures, including the German Need for Touch scale and the BFI-K. In the exploratory phase, participants wore a binocular eye-tracker and first visually, then haptically, explored the materials while verbalizing their impressions. Three video cameras recorded hand movements and facial expressions. Stimuli were presented in three randomized blocks with short breaks between blocks. In the rating phase, participants completed a Touch Perception Task (TPT) and rated each texture on 14 sensory and aesthetic descriptors using seven-point Likert scales; re-exploration during rating was allowed when needed. The full procedure lasted approximately 90 minutes.

3 Preliminary Findings and Discussion

The preliminary findings reported here are based on descriptive analyses of Touch Perception Task ratings and think-aloud data, combined with an initial comparison of visual and haptic evaluations across materials. Analyses of eye-tracking, video-recorded exploration, and individual-difference measures are ongoing.

First, the materials elicited distinct perceptual-affective profiles that broadly align with previous work in haptic aesthetics, but not in a purely linear way. Sandpapers were generally judged as rough, firm, and irritating, whereas silks were more often described as smooth, warm, and pleasant. However, several materials showed less intuitive profiles, suggesting that material evaluation cannot be reduced to simple physical properties alone.

Second, the current data suggest that visuo-tactile congruency plays an important role in material appraisal. In several cases, visual anticipation did not fully match haptic experience. A particularly informative example concerns the contrast between coarse sandpaper K40 (425 μm average particle diameter) and much finer sandpaper K1200 (15 μm average particle diameter). K40 was initially visually engaging because of its novelty, color ambiguity, and light reflection, and was subsequently experienced as more interesting and less unpleasant than expected upon touch. By contrast, K1200 appeared visually less salient, yet was experienced as less pleasant haptically because of a subtle tactile resistance. This pattern suggests that direct contact can refine, moderate, or even reverse initial visual appraisal.

Third, the preliminary findings indicate that haptic engagement is not driven by pleasantness alone. Some of the most engaging materials were not those with the highest immediate hedonic value, but those that combined perceptual challenge with tactile safety. This is consistent with the idea that moderately complex or ambiguous materials may sustain interest because they require further sensory verification, rather than because they are simply soft or fluent. Qualitative reports support this interpretation, repeatedly referring to novelty, irregularity, ambiguity, safety, and tactile invitation or avoidance.

Finally, the dataset points to substantial individual variation in both evaluation and exploration. This is relevant because it suggests that visuo-tactile material perception is shaped not only by stimulus properties, but also by touch-related dispositions and broader person-level differences. As a work in progress, the study does not yet provide a final integrative model. Even so, the present findings already support a more process-oriented account of material perception, in which visual anticipation, direct touch, and evaluative meaning are tightly coupled during exploration.

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